

A New Sensitive and Selective Reagent for Extraction of Trace Amount Molybdenum in Iso-Amyl Alcohol and Photometric Determination

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INSPITE of the large number of thio-ligands being utilized in analytical chemistry, a very limited number of thiols as photometric reagents for the determination of molybdenum(VI) is known¹⁻⁶. Solvent extraction studies of coloured chelates formed by Mo(VI) with a few thiols were reported earlier⁷⁻⁹. Dithiol has been extensively used in a large number of applications¹⁰⁻¹².

In the present study a mercapto compound, β -mercapto-resorcylic acid, has been employed as a chelating agent for molybdenum for its solvent extraction and photometric determination. The thiol reagent reacts with Mo(VI) to form a stable violet chelate extractable into iso-amyl alcohol. The complex extracted from 2 M HCl medium absorbs at 490 nm.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer, with matched 1 cm glass cells, was used for all absorbance measurements.

Reagents and solvents: Ammonium heptamolybdate octahydrate was dissolved in water containing a few drops of ammonia. The metal content of the solution was estimated by oxine method¹³. Solutions of varying strengths were prepared by dilution of the stock. A 0.5% solution of the reagent was prepared by dissolving the β -mercapto-resorcylic acid in double distilled water. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their soluble salts and were standardized by conventional procedures. Iso-amyl alcohol (E. Merck, G. R.) was directly used for extraction.

Preparation of β -mercapto-resorcylic acid: The reagent was prepared following the method of Pantletschke and Benger¹⁴. A 0.5% reagent solution was prepared by dissolving the weighed amount in 100 ml of 0.1 M NaOH and warming it for 10 min at 60° under N₂. The solution was neutralised with acetic acid or hydrochloric acid under cold condition. The reagent solution is stable only for 6 hr at room temperature and should be prepared fresh before use.

Extraction procedure: A known amount of molybdenum(VI) solution (50-100 μ g/ml) is taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel with 5 ml of 0.5% reagent solution and 5 ml of 6 M hydrochloric acid. Water is added to make up the volume of the aqueous phase to 15 ml. The violet molybdenum complex is extracted by shaking for 5 min with

10 ml of iso-amyl alcohol followed by 3 $\times$ 5 ml portions of the solvent. The combined extract is dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with iso-amyl alcohol. The absorbance of the complex is measured at 490 nm against a solvent blank.

Procedure for alloy steel: 0.5 g of the steel sample is dissolved in 50 ml of 3 M sulphuric acid and the solution digested on a hot plate, with repeated addition of acid, to a syrupy consistency and treated with 5 ml of conc. nitric acid for complete digestion. The solution is evaporated on a hot plate until fumes of sulphur dioxide are evolved. It is diluted with 50 ml of water, boiled and filtered. The filtrate and washings are collected in a 250 ml volumetric flask and made upto the mark. The molybdenum content is determined by the above stated procedure using ascorbic acid as masking agent.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum: The absorption spectrum of the complex (Mo, 4 ppm) extracted from 2 M HCl taken in the wavelength region 450-700 nm shows a maximum at 490 (violet) measured against solvent blank. The reagent blank shows no absorption at this wavelength.

Optimum conditions for complex formation: The optimum range of reagent concentrations is 3 to 10 ml of 0.5% reagent solution. 5 ml of the solution was used for each measurement.

The optimum acid concentration for maximum colour development was 1.5-4.5 M HCl. Extractions and measurements were made at 2 M HCl. Quantitative extraction was achieved with 5 min of shaking. The molybdenum complex was found to be stable in the solvent for 6 hr at room temperature.

Beer's law, optimum range, photometric error and sensitivity: Measurements of absorbances of a series of molybdenum complex extracts containing varied amounts of Mo(VI) were made at 490 nm against the solvent blank. The system adheres to Beer's law from 0.25 to 8 ppm of molybdenum(VI). The optimum range of determination, obtained from Ringbom's plot is 1-5 ppm. The % relative error per 1% absolute photometric error following Ayres' equation is 2.71. The molar absorptivity of the complex and Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction are 1.94×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.00492 μ g cm⁻² of Mo(VI), respectively.

Composition of the complex: The plot of absorbance against the mole-fraction of the metal M/(M+R) shows a sharp break at 1:2 (M:R) composition at 490 nm. The mole ratio plot gives the same composition (1:2) with 1.042×10^{-3} M metal and reagent solutions.

Degree of dissociation and stepwise and overall stability constants: The degree of dissociation, α , was calculated from Harvey-Manning's equation¹⁵

TABLE 1—STEPWISE AND OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE MOLYBDENUM COMPLEX (1 : 2) AT 28 ± 1°

Harvey-Manning's method					Leden's method			Yatsimirskii's method		
A_m	A_s	α	C	log K	log K_1	log K_2	log K	log K_1	log K_2	log K
0.812	0.648	0.202	$4.169 \times 10^{-5} M$	10.14	5.01	4.85	9.86	5.16	4.85	10.01

and the instability constant K' was evaluated from the formula $K' = 4\alpha^2 C^2 / 1 - \alpha$ for a 1 : 2 complex (C is the total analytical concentration of the complex). The stepwise stability constants K_1 and K_2 were evaluated by Leden's and Yatsimirskii's methods^{15,16}. The values are reported in Table 1.

Effect of diverse ions : The tolerance limits for the interfering ions added separately for 4 ppm molybdenum(VI) metal in the final extract were determined at 490 nm. A change of 0.005 absorbance unit at 490 nm was taken as the standard. At 2 M HCl acidity 5 times excess of almost all the metal ions excepting W(VI), Re(VII), Fe(III), Pd(II) have been tolerated. Masking with fluoride removed the interference of Fe(III) and tolerance limit increased to 20 ppm. 50 ppm each of sulphate, nitrate, phosphate, citrate, tartrate, fluoride, EDTA, oxalate did not interfere in the determination. The tolerance limits of the interfering ions increased if a higher acidity (3.5 M HCl) was maintained for extractions.

Analysis of high-speed steel (BAS 60 b) : A number of determinations were made with the steel solution. Average of several such determinations of the standard steel gave a result of 0.42% Mo (certified value, 0.43% Mo).

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